

Accessible Musical ALife Through LLM Co-Creation

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Abstract

GPU-accelerated artificial life (ALife) simulations offer rich possibilities for musical expression, but building them demands programming fluency that excludes many musicians and sound artists. We present a natural language interface that translates behavioral descriptions into executable particle simulations with integrated Open Sound Control output and SuperCollider companion patches. A preliminary evaluation across three frontier models suggests that structured context engineering is necessary for reliable code synthesis, while extensive documentation alone yields no improvement over unassisted generation. The pipeline’s value lies in overcoming the *cold start* of domain specific languages (DSLs), producing a bespoke first sketch the musician refines through conversation. Source code and evaluation scripts are available at <https://github.com/mclemcrew/tolvera>.

CCS Concepts

• **Applied computing** → **Sound and music computing**; • **Computing methodologies** → **Artificial life**; Natural language processing; • **Human-centered computing** → *Interactive systems and tools*.

Keywords

Artificial Life, Musical Interface, LLM Code Synthesis, OSC, Sonification, Context Engineering

1 Introduction

Artificial Life (ALife), the synthesis of life-like processes in non-biological media [13], offers musicians an alternative to parameter mapping: rather than automating control curves, the artist tends an ecosystem of agents whose emergent behaviors drive composition [21, 22]. GPU-accelerated ALife simulation, however, demands fluency in kernel compilation, parallel data structures, and framework-specific constraints [10], creating a barrier for musicians whose expertise lies elsewhere [4, 23].

Large language models (LLMs) appear to offer a bridge, translating behavioral descriptions into executable code. In practice, even frontier models fail to generate valid code for specialized GPU frameworks regardless of how much documentation they receive [14]. We present a natural language interface that addresses this gap, generating GPU-accelerated particle simulations with integrated Open Sound Control (OSC) [27] output and SuperCollider [16] companion patches.

Our preliminary evaluation suggests that structured context engineering (decomposing prompts and selecting targeted domain knowledge) is necessary for reliable synthesis, while extensive documentation alone does not help. The same pipeline generalizes across frontier models without model-specific tuning, suggesting that targeting smaller open-weight models may paradoxically require establishing such pipelines on frontier models first. The pipeline’s principal value lies in overcoming the *cold start* of domain specific languages (DSLs), producing a bespoke first sketch the musician refines through conversation. Source code and evaluation scripts are available at <https://github.com/mclemcrew/tolvera>.

2 Related Work

Wekinator [7] established that interactive machine learning can be made accessible to musicians without machine learning expertise, a precedent our work extends to GPU-accelerated ALife. Creative coding environments such as Processing [20], TidalCycles [17], and LLM-powered tools such as Spellburst [2] have further lowered the barrier to artistic computation [12]. NIME practice, however, remains predicated on domain-specific languages (e.g., SuperCollider [16], ChucK [26], Faust [19], CSound [25]), for which LLMs have significantly less training data than general-purpose languages [11]. GPU frameworks such as Taichi [10] compound this, requiring kernel compilation and parallel data layout that creative coding environments do not abstract away.

While LLMs demonstrate strong synthesis for general-purpose languages [6], domain-specific frameworks pose distinct challenges general models cannot reliably handle [8]. Zhang et al. [28] benchmark LLM generation for audio programming and find

Figure 1: Output of the illustrative example. Three species of flocking particles with diffusion trails. Each species’ leader particle streams position and velocity data via OSC to a dedicated SuperCollider SynthDef, producing a three-voice evolving texture driven by spatial movement.

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Figure 2: System pipeline. A natural language description is decomposed into atomic behavioral components, enriched with dynamically-selected domain context, synthesized as individual GPU expert functions, and composed into an executable sketch with optional OSC output and SuperCollider companion scripts.

that structured approaches yield more correct output, corroborating our findings. Promising mitigations include type-constrained decoding [18], monitor-guided decoding that enables smaller models to match frontier ones [1], and low-rank adaptation on curated DSL corpora [24].

At the intersection of ALife and music, Lucas et al. [15] demonstrated interactive sonification of swarmalator systems at NIME, treating swarm dynamics as a real-time sound source. We extend this direction by using LLMs to translate natural language *intent* into executable GPU code driving both visual and sonic output.

3 System Overview

To address these technical barriers, we extend Tólvera [3], an ALife framework for composable agents, with a system that translates natural language behavior descriptions into executable particle simulations via Taichi [10]. The pipeline is carried out in four stages. First, an LLM decomposes the user’s description into atomic behavioral components, identifying species, state variables, and musical intent. A second LLM call selects relevant domain knowledge modules (typically 3–5), acting as a lightweight retrieval step. Each component is then synthesized as an individual GPU kernel function, constrained by the selected context and typing rules. We term these synthesized functions *experts*, inspired by the Product of Experts formulation [9], as the final behavior emerges from their combination. Finally, Jinja2¹ templates compose the experts into a complete executable sketch.

3.1 Sonification & OSC Integration

When a user’s prompt contains musical keywords (e.g., “sonify,” “sound,” “rhythm,” “musical”), the system generates OSC mappings alongside the visual simulation. A dedicated module selects per-species metrics (position, velocity, density, separation), and emits smoothing kernels for stable real-time control. Because OSC is host-agnostic, any OSC-capable environment can consume these streams; we provide a SuperCollider companion patch as a reference mapping (position to pitch over 80–3000 Hz exponentially, velocity to amplitude, density to filter cutoff).

3.2 Illustrative Example

To illustrate the pipeline, we prompted the system with “*three species of particles that flock together and sonify their movements with different timbres.*” The decomposer identified four expert types (separation, cohesion, alignment, wander), the context selector retrieved the flocking and OSC modules, and each expert was synthesized individually before composition into a complete sketch streaming three independent OSC channels (one per species).

We routed these to a SuperCollider companion patch with three SynthDefs (saw, FM, pulse) mapping position to pitch and velocity to amplitude.

4 Evaluation

We compared the context-engineered pipeline against unassisted frontier models on 8 prompts with binary pass/fail. The pass criterion (error-free execution for 12 seconds) checks syntactic and runtime correctness only, not behavioral fidelity or musical utility; user studies addressing those dimensions are future work. Prompts span four difficulty levels (T1: single-particle physics, T2: pairwise interactions, T3: multi-species behaviors, T4: complex multi-component systems), each containing 2 prompts with musical/OSC intent. Given the sample size, results are illustrative of qualitative differences between conditions rather than performance claims.

4.1 Benchmark Results

Table 1: Execution pass rate by model, condition, and difficulty tier. Each cell shows passes out of 2 prompts. All prompts include musical/OSC intent.

Model	Condition	T1	T2	T3	T4	Total
Sonnet 4.5	Zero-shot	0/2	0/2	0/2	0/2	0/8
	Full codebase	0/2	0/2	0/2	0/2	0/8
	Pipeline	2/2	1/2	2/2	1/2	6/8
Opus 4.6	Zero-shot	0/2	0/2	0/2	0/2	0/8
	Full codebase	0/2	0/2	0/2	0/2	0/8
	Pipeline	1/2	1/2	2/2	1/2	5/8
DeepSeek v3	Zero-shot	0/2	0/2	0/2	0/2	0/8
	Full codebase	0/2	0/2	0/2	0/2	0/8
	Pipeline	1/2	1/2	1/2	1/2	4/8

We tested three conditions: (A) zero-shot with minimal framework context, (B) full codebase documentation as system context, and (C) our context-engineered pipeline. Table 1 shows conditions A and B achieve 0% execution across all models, while the pipeline produces runnable sketches at 75% (Sonnet), 62% (Opus), and 50% (DeepSeek). Dominant failures without the pipeline include hallucinated APIs (e.g., `osc.create_client()`) and GPU-specific syntax violations. Condition B offered no measurable improvement over zero-shot, possibly because irrelevant API surface introduces noise rather than informing generation. Selective context (3–5 targeted modules) outperformed providing all

¹<https://jinjapalletsprojects.com/en/stable/>

modules at once, suggesting that *how* context is structured matters more than *how much*.

4.2 Frontier vs. Local Models

Local models offer openness and offline capability but failed to satisfy Taichi’s strict typing and kernel constraints even within our pipeline, often hallucinating standard Python functions (e.g., `random.random()`) inside GPU kernels where framework-specific intrinsics (e.g., `ti.random()`) are required. Frontier models succeeded only when constrained by the pipeline, suggesting pipeline architecture may matter more than raw model capability for this class of task.

5 Discussion

5.1 Iteration vs. Generation

A recurring challenge in algorithmic composition is starting from zero. LLMs are better at *iterating* on existing code than at *creating* from a blank slate; in our informal testing, all models could make meaningful changes to an existing sketch, but generation from nothing almost always failed. Specialized GPU frameworks intensify the gap, since iteration presupposes producing the boilerplate to get the first pixel on screen. The system therefore functions less as a composer than as a means of overcoming the activation energy needed to initialize a complex ALife sketch, so the musician can begin refining immediately. Refining generated code still benefits from programming familiarity, but the distance between modifying a working sketch and writing one from scratch is substantially smaller. Our correctness-oriented evaluation also misses an important dimension of creative value: each generation introduces different details and small deviations that can themselves be artistically productive, echoing creative coding’s tradition of serendipitous bugs yielding unexpected directions [5].

5.2 Constrained Generation Beats Larger Models

We initially prioritized openness, but smaller models required prompt optimization that the rapid release cycle of new models frequently rendered obsolete. Comprehensive framework documentation did not yield measurable improvement over unassisted generation. In contrast, a pipeline defined by prompt decomposition and context selection produced working sketches across frontier models without model-specific tuning. Our small sample suggests reliability may stem from architectural context engineering rather than raw model capability; future work targeting smaller models will likely require establishing baselines on frontier models first.

5.3 Accessibility & Openness

Pairing visual simulations with a SuperCollider companion lowers the barrier for practitioners without GPU programming skills. A tension remains between capability and openness: frontier models are closed-source and commercially hosted, while open-weight alternatives that run locally and can be inspected by the community cannot yet satisfy the strict constraints of GPU kernel synthesis. Since NIME practice broadly relies on DSLs, this *openness-capability gap* extends beyond our system [11]. Constrained decoding and domain-specific fine-tuning (Section 2) offer promising directions for closing it while preserving artist autonomy.

6 Ethics Statement

Large language models are both the subject and a tool of this research. The pipeline evaluates frontier models (Sonnet 4.5, Opus 4.6, DeepSeek v3) as components of a code synthesis system, and all generated outputs are clearly identified as such throughout the paper. Original drafting, argumentation, and analysis were completed by the human authors; Claude Code and Gemini were subsequently used as reviewing tools to surface poor phrasing, weak arguments, and logical gaps, with all final editorial decisions remaining with the human authors.

The evaluation is fully automated, scored by subprocess execution, and involved no human participants; user studies of creative affordances and accessibility are future work and will be conducted under institutional ethics review. We designed the system to lower the barrier to GPU-accelerated musical ALife for practitioners whose expertise lies in composition rather than kernel programming, and the source code and evaluation scripts are released under an open-source license to support community access and reproducibility.

We acknowledge the computational costs of this work, which include repeated LLM inference calls to commercially hosted models during development and evaluation, as well as GPU execution of Taichi simulations. Individual sketch generation is modest, but iterative benchmarking across multiple models and conditions accumulates non-trivial energy expenditure. Finally, as discussed in Section 5.3, a tension exists between the capability of closed-source frontier models and the values of openness and artist autonomy that inform NIME practice; we view constrained decoding and domain-specific fine-tuning as promising directions for closing this gap.

7 Conclusion

We have presented a natural language interface for musical ALife co-creation. Our preliminary results suggest structured context engineering is necessary for reliable synthesis in specialized creative frameworks, and that the pipeline’s value lies in overcoming the *cold start* of specialized syntax. Larger-scale evaluation is needed, but these observations may be of use to others building LLM-powered tools for creative communities where the gap between artistic intent and technical implementation remains wide.

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